

Laudenbach, F. & Anslinger, E. (2019). Labour market mobility into and within Germany – Demands, possibilities and effectiveness. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.347-352) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641762>

Labour market mobility into and within Germany – Demands, possibilities and effectiveness

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Abstract

This paper comparatively analyses the impact and functionality of the Federal Recognition Act as well as the external examination. Both approaches can foster labour mobility into and within the German labour market. Focusing on horizontal mobility as a spatial movement of migrants and vertical mobility as an upskilling movement, we link these approaches with individual perspectives and experiences. The results show that both approaches highly depend on the formal education system. For the individuals this linkage can have an effect of exclusion and devaluation but also can have a motivating effect. With regard to their labour market integration, both approaches can enable a sustainable mobility into and within the German labour market. Nevertheless, those processes are very demanding and rely on strict regulations that can impede a smooth procedure.

Keywords

mobility; labour market; recognition of prior learning; upskilling pathways

1 Introduction

In 2010, the European Union declared the importance of labour mobility in its Europe 2020 strategy „to respond in a flexible way to the priorities and needs of labour markets“ (European Commission 2010: 17). In Germany, the Federal Recognition Act was passed in 2012 to enable the recognition of foreign qualifications, taking a fundamental step to comply with the politically desired wish to increase labour mobility and to cope with domestic skill shortages. At the same time the German VET landscape usually refers to the external examination as another means to enter the German labour market with an officially recognized qualification. In contrast to the Federal Recognition Act, the external examination is an instrument with a long tradition which is widely accepted in the German labour market. The linkage of these two approaches is that they both can foster labour market mobility – into and within the German labour market.

This paper aims to shed light on whether these instruments enable labour market mobility and improve the personal situation of individuals in the German labour market. Based on qualitative interviews with individuals who have undergone a recognition process or an external examination, this paper uncovers the experiences they have gathered during these processes, whether their non-formal and informal competences have been considered and how their upskilling pathways have been accepted by the labour market.

By comparing the Recognition Act and the external examination with regard to their impact on labour market mobility of individuals, we link the individual perspective with the institutional level and shed light on how these two instruments – the one rather new, whilst the other with a long tradition in the German VET-landscape – can foster labour market mobility.

2 Defining labour market mobility

Labour and labour market structures are more and more affected by changes. Research confirms an increasing flexibility in the labour market as well as for the employees working within this labour market (Voß/Pongratz 1998; Struck 2006; Seifert/Struck 2009; Erlinghagen 2017). These changes affect questions of trajectories of employment and conditions of employment equally. At the same time these trends imply a higher need of labour market mobility and a flexible adaptation of individuals to the needs of the labour market.

From a European perspective, labour market mobility is usually linked with the idea of free movement. This concept is being described as a means to enable a flexible supply to the demands of labour in different member states and within the member states (Guild 1999). This shall create an efficient European labour market and at the same time allows individuals to improve their employment prospective as well as employers to recruit suitable employees (Boswell/Geddes 2011: 81-82; Fassmann/Lane 2009: 2).

As labour market mobility can comprise an individual work life dimension as well as an institutional cross-national dimension, we define labour mobility in a twofold way: (1) we define labour mobility as an approach that is shaped by the European idea of free movement and thus enables a horizontal mobility. Horizontal mobility relates to the cross-national movement or migration of a person into or within the EU (and Germany) with the aim to improve their labour market prospective. More precisely, it refers to the spatial movement of persons from one country to another and includes their aim to get full recognition of their qualifications at the host country. (2) We define vertical mobility which refers to the upward movement of persons from being unskilled to being skilled and thus having their competences officially recognized. This relates to the idea of intragenerational mobility, “a process (which) unfolds in the course of the worklife” (Allmendinger 1990: 3). At the same time it depends on the permeability of the education system and the labour market (Allmendinger 1990). The result of vertical mobility shall be an official certification or qualification proving the person’s competences.

Recognizing prior learning is considered to increase the labour market mobility and inclusion of individuals (Schöpf 2015). Particularly for the low skilled workers and workers in non-standard employment increasing the transparency and usability of non-formal and informal learning outcomes can support them in overcoming precarious employment and working conditions. Additionally, in labour market segments and sectors where skills gaps are an issue of concern, the recognition of already existing skills and competences of individuals can bring qualified people into work more quickly (Dobischat and Schurgatz 2015: 34). Consequently, it is worth to scrutinize whether the existing approaches in Germany can foster horizontal and vertical mobility and how they are structured formally and institutionally.

3 External examination and Recognition Act: German approaches to regulate labour market mobility?

The question of skill shortages is of high relevance for the German labour market (Bellmann et al. 2015; Bossler et al. 2018). Shortage occupations, such as in the care professions in Germany, determine the labour market and are often open to unskilled and low skilled workers as well as migrants. By recognizing their qualifications as well as their non-formal and informal competences, the Recognition Act and the external examination can path the way for those

workers to enter the German labour market. Both approaches will be described in the following briefly:

The external examination is an approach which enables the recognition of prior learning by facilitating the permission for taking an external examination that forms part of the formal education system. For vocational training, this procedure was established in the 1960s to give people not formally trained under the dual apprenticeship program the chance to acquire a formal vocational qualification. According to the National Vocational Qualification Law (§45 (2) BBiG) and regulations set up by the chamber of crafts (§37 (2) HwO), people are allowed to apply for taking the final examination without having attended the respective vocational training program if they comply with certain requirements, including the proof of relevant work experience covering 1.5 times the duration of the regular training program. Alternatively, it is also possible to prove that relevant competences have been acquired in other ways.

The Federal Recognition Act was introduced in April 2012 to enable the recognition of equivalence of prior learning to national education standards and certificates. It guarantees individuals the right to get foreign qualifications recognized by a competent authority within three months as being equal to a respective national qualification. The recognition process is, in the first place, based on assessing relevant documents such as training certificates, certificates of capability and proofs of relevant domain-specific work experience acquired in a foreign country or in Germany (see § 3 BQFG section 1). Complementary, competence assessment is also possible based on practical tests, work proofs and interviews. When significant skill gaps impede full recognition, a partial recognition can be awarded that can be supplemented, for example, by further training (Böse et al. 2014).

Both approaches are linked to the formal education system of Germany. The former results in a formal examination, which officially proves the skills and competences of a person. The latter is an equivalence assessment which proves that the foreign qualification is equal to the German qualification. Together, they offer a pathway to skilled work and an instrument to increase vertical as well as horizontal mobility. Nevertheless, they both rely on strict regulations and high standards that are defined by the formal education system. Against this backdrop it has to be scrutinized which impact these approaches have for low skilled workers and migrants. This paper empirically provides a first proof of opportunities regarding mobility for low skilled and migrant workers in the German labour market.

4 Insights into labour market mobility – stories of recognition and devaluation

In the previous section, we outlined the institutional structure of the approaches facilitating mobility to low skilled workers and migrants in Germany. In this section we refer to the individual level and present their experiences with the institutional structure.

Our analysis is based on problem centred interviews (Witzel 2000) with 13 individuals that have either undergone an external examination or a recognition of their foreign qualification. Through a qualitative content analysis, these interviews were analysed focussing on their biographical development, their spatial or intragenerational mobility and on the challenges experienced during their recognition process/external examination. The following sections summarize the results of our analysis.

4.1 Vertical and horizontal mobility

For our analysis we interviewed 7 individuals who have applied for recognition of their foreign qualifications. Those individuals whose education was not similar to the German education system had difficulties to immediately receive a full recognition and, hence, to get access to the German labour market. In these cases, labour market mobility was only possible indirectly by restarting education. For example, one interviewee had to restart a vocational educa-

tion and training due to the fact that his school-leaving qualification was not assessed as being equal to the German qualification. Non-formally and informally acquired competences did not play an important role during the recognition processes.

Furthermore, we interviewed 6 individuals that have undergone an external examination. In these cases, the result of the external examination is the official and formal qualification (in the respective profession) and therefore has a high recognition in the German labour market. Consequently, their inclusion into the German labour market was successful. For example, one interviewee worked for years in temporary jobs in the housekeeping sector. By completing an external examination, the interviewee could receive an official qualification as housekeeper. Informally acquired competences could be considered in this example, as the working experiences were accepted as proof of the necessary working experiences.

The recognition of foreign qualifications let individuals work and earn according to their qualifications after the assessment. This allows moving to a new country, while having the same opportunities to work as in the country of origin – at least theoretically. Most of the interviewees had to restart education or to complete compensatory measures. This means that they could work equivalently only after another period of training. Likewise, the external examination facilitates an intragenerational mobility of low skilled workers and hereby enables integration into the German labour market as skilled workers.

4.2 Individual effects of labour market mobility

On the structural level, both approaches resulted in labour market mobility – one at an earlier stage while the other often later. On the individual level they both have effects that are not necessarily identical:

On the one hand, several of the interviewees that applied for recognition of their qualification felt devaluated. Although they already had worked in their profession and/or had completed a qualification in their country of origin, they had to prove their competences and skills once again. Several of the interviewees had to restart their training or parts of it. They personally felt devaluated and discouraged by the recognition process. At the same time, the other interviewees personally had no problems with their recognition process. They indicated that they felt quite confident due to the encouraging counselling process before the application.

On the other hand, the interviewees that completed an external examination had a positive effect. Most of the interviewees returned to work after a long break but had difficulties to return to their original profession. They either felt not up-to-date within their profession or wanted to change their profession. The official proof of having the competences in the respective profession resulted in an encouraging effect for the individuals. They admitted to feel more self-confident due to the accomplished effort. They even continued their learning effort and conducted further training to become a responsible manager. Nevertheless, they all admitted that it was a very challenging process to learn for an exam on their own while continuing their usual work. Moreover, it was a challenge for them to take an exam after a long period without any school education.

With regard to the labour market perspectives on labour mobility, the interviewees indicated that with the support and inclusion of the employer, they perceived the processes as more successful and easier. The interviewees that conducted an external examination indicated that the employer even initiated those processes.

With a view to skill shortages in certain professions in the German labour market it could also be of relevance to consider informal and non-formal competences that individuals have acquired during their lifetime. Our interviewees indicated that those competences only played a minor role. In the present cases of external examinations the recognition of non-formal and informal competences paved the way to the formal examination. Experiences of child-raising (parental leave) or care of relatives could be considered as working experiences. Especially in

the cases under the recognition act, the decisive factor of the equivalence assessment was the proof of formal education. Only with this proof, informal and non-formal competences could be considered during the recognition process.

5 Conclusion

Our study serves as a first insight into the impact and functionality of the Recognition Act as well as the external examination with regard to labour mobility of low skilled workers and migrants into and within the German labour market. Our results show that it highly depends on the formal education system whether mobility (horizontal and vertical) is successful. Consequently, on the individual level those processes can have both devaluating and encouraging effects. Informal and non-formal competences can only pave the way into a formal examination; in the recognition process they only play a minor role. This pathway through the formal education system in both cases entails high standards that are very demanding for both low skilled workers and migrants.

Having in mind the present shortage of skilled workers in Germany especially in the care sector or in the electrical engineering, procedures and further education that streamline horizontal and vertical mobility for different target groups in the long-term seem to be necessary. Therefore, it seems indispensable to create flexible gateways to the formal (vocational) education system.

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